

Exploring the Effect of Sensorineural Hearing Loss on Wideband Acoustic Immittance Using the NHANES Dataset

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Abstract. Wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) responses have been demonstrated to have significant clinical utility in the differential diagnosis of middle (and in some cases, inner) ear pathologies.¹ While these measurements assess the mechanical transduction of sound through the ear and are thus sensitive to pathologies that influence the conductive mechanics of the auditory system (e.g., otitis media, otosclerosis, ossicular disarticulation, and semicircular canal dehiscence), recent work suggests that WAI may also be impacted by sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL)². However, due to age differences present in comparison groups in that work, it is not clear whether the observed effects were due to age, SNHL, or a combination of the two. Thus, the goal of this study was to determine whether SNHL associations with WAI absorbance (WAI-A) measurements vary when compared to a control population stratified by age, and if so, whether severity of hearing loss also plays a role.

We analyzed WAI-A data collected by the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES). Two publicly available NHANES datasets that include WAI-A measurements were analyzed. Ears meeting criteria for normal hearing and SNHL of varying degrees (a mild-to-moderate group and a severe-to-profound group) for 50 to 80-year-old participants were identified. WAI-A responses were extracted for each ear identified and analyzed for validity. Valid measurements for the three groups (normal hearing, SNHL mild-to-moderate, and SNHL severe-to-profound) were compared to determine whether SNHL systematically alters WAI-A responses.

The two NHANES datasets were analyzed separately because preliminary results suggest that there may be systematic differences between them. The first dataset included 50-69-year-old-participants while the second included 70-79-year-old participants. For the 50-69-year-olds, no statistically significant differences were observed between normal hearing ears (N=674) and either SNHL group (N=45 mild-to-moderate, N=9 severe-to-profound). For the 70-79-year-olds, limited statistically significant differences were observed between the normal hearing ears (N=66) and ears with mild-to-moderate (N=45) and severe-to-profound (N=8) SNHL. These differences occurred at four frequencies (all 343-408 Hz) for the mild-to-moderate SNHL cohort and at five frequencies (all 2000-2245 Hz) for the severe-to-profound cohort. Since there were measurements at 107 frequencies, if there were no differences and associations were independent at each frequency, we would expect about 5 tests to have a p-value less than 0.05. It is notable that the frequencies where differences occurred were not consistent with those found by Attias and colleagues.² Overall, our preliminary results suggest that SNHL is unlikely to have a notable effect on WAI-A.

INTRODUCTION

Wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) responses have been demonstrated to have significant clinical utility in the differential diagnosis of middle (and in some cases, inner) ear pathologies.¹ While these measurements assess the mechanical transduction of sound through the ear and are thus sensitive to pathologies that influence the conductive mechanics of the auditory system (e.g., otitis media, otosclerosis, ossicular disarticulation, and semicircular canal dehiscence), recent work also suggests that wideband acoustic immittance may also be impacted by sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL).²

Attias and colleagues² found a decrease in wideband acoustic immittance absorbance (WAI-A) around 4–5 kHz in ears with severe-to-profound SNHL as compared to normal ears.² While the mechanism of a change in WAI-A due to SNHL is not clear, the authors hypothesized that this difference could be due to structural and mechanical changes in the Organ of Corti including loss or atrophy of cochlear neurons and sensory cells, labyrinthine fibrosis, tectorial membrane abnormalities, and/or changes in cochlear partition micromechanics. However, the normal ears in that study were from a group of individuals substantially younger in age than the ears with severe-to-profound hearing loss. As such, the differences observed could be due to this difference in age and not SNHL. Indeed, prior work has demonstrated differences in WAI-A due to older age.^{3,4} Thus, the goal of this study was to determine whether SNHL influences WAI-A measurements as compared to an age-matched control population, and if so, whether severity of hearing loss also plays a role.

Recruiting a sizeable population of individuals with SNHL, particularly those who do not currently wear cochlear implants (as the presence of a cochlear implant can alter WAI-A responses^{5,6}) and no co-occurring middle-ear pathologies (as these would also alter WAI-A responses^{7,8}), likely means recruiting many older adults. This, in turn, would require recruiting a sizeable age-matched group of older adults with normal hearing for comparison. Given the incidence of hearing loss in older adults, recruitment of normal controls for a prospective study of this sort would be challenging.

Because of this limitation, we chose to answer this question through analysis of WAI-A data collected by the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES). The NHANES program, which sits within the Center for Disease Control and Prevention's National Center for Health Statistics, collects a wide range of health-related survey and measurement data from a representative population across the United States. Data collected starting in 2015 includes both WAI and audiometric data from a large number of participants with varying degrees of hearing loss. Sun and colleagues³ recently utilized this database to explore the effect of age on individuals with normal hearing in a large number of subjects. Using a similar approach here, we define and extract audiometric and WAI data from the NHANES database for three groups, normal hearing, mild-to-severe SNHL, and severe-to-profound SNHL, to determine the association of SNHL with WAI-A measurements.

METHODS

Two independent sets of wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) data have been published on the NHANES data website. The 2015–2016 NHANES data includes WAI measurements on subjects ages 20 to 69 years, and the 2017–2020 NHANES data include WAI measurements on subjects ages 6 to 19 and 70 to 80 years. WAI measurements in this database were made at ambient pressure with the Interacoustics Titan in response to a wideband click stimulus from 226-8000 Hz.

Data were retrieved from both databases using methods described previously.³ Briefly, WAI quantities of absorbance (WAI-A) and admittance angle at ambient pressure were extracted from the database using MATLAB. WAI responses were included for ears that met inclusion criteria for this study based on audiometric findings. For the purposes of this work, inclusion criteria for ears with SNHL included (1) normal otoscopy, (2) tympanometric peak pressure in the range –50 to 50 daPa, (3) tympanometric compliance in the range 0.3 to 1.5 mmho, and (4) pure-tone audiometric thresholds either in the mild-to-severe range (≥ 25 dB HL at 500 Hz, ≥ 35 dB HL at 1000 Hz, and ≥ 40 dB HL from 2000-8000 Hz) or severe-to-profound range (≥ 30 dB HL at 500 Hz, ≥ 60 dB HL at 1000 Hz, and ≥ 70 dB HL from 2000-8000 Hz). Ears with SNHL were compared to normal control ears, stratified by decade of age. Inclusion criteria

for normal control ears included (1) normal otoscopy, (2) tympanometric peak pressure in the range -50 to 50 daPa, (3) tympanometric compliance in the range 0.3 to 1.5 mmho, and (4) pure-tone audiometric thresholds ≤ 25 dB at frequencies 500 , 1000 , 2000 , and 4000 Hz and ≤ 40 dB HL at 8000 Hz. Note that data from adults coded as age 80 were not included, as adults were coded as 80 even if their age exceeded 80 and thus, we could not appropriately determine their age within a decade of life. Once WAI data were extracted based on inclusion criteria, the WAI data were then assessed for quality and leaks via a data selection criteria algorithm that was developed by Sun and colleagues.³ Data that did not pass the selection criteria were excluded.

Analyses of WAI-A across the three groups categorized as Normal, SNHL Mild-to-Severe, and SNHL Severe-to-Profound were performed in MATLAB (The Mathworks, version R2023b). At each of 107 frequencies, first, the function ``anova1'' was used to determine a table of statistics that was then used for multiple comparison tests. Next, the MATLAB function ``multcompare'' performed a multiple comparison at a 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$) using Tukey's honestly significant difference procedure to allow pairwise comparison of the means between the three groups while maintaining our alpha level within frequencies. The resulting p values are plotted here to compare Normal with each of the two SNHL groups. There were no adjustments for testing for multiple frequencies. For this work, if there were no differences and associations were independent at each frequency, we would expect 5.35 (5% of 107 tests) to have a p-value less than 0.05 .

RESULTS

Investigating Differences in Age and Dataset

As we are investigating effects in two independent datasets, our first analysis explored normal WAI-A responses from each dataset by decade of life. In completing this analysis, we noticed a systematic difference between the two datasets, in that the data collected in $2015-2016$ reflects lower WAI-A in the $1000-4000$ Hz range as compared to data collected in $2017-2020$. Given that ears in the $2017-2020$ cohort are both younger and older than ears in the $2015-2016$ cohort, we suspect this is a systematic difference between the datasets (perhaps due to changes in measurement procedures, calibrations, or equipment) as opposed to an age effect, and as such, felt that the datasets could not be compiled for further analyses and had to be kept separate.

FIGURE 1. Mean WAI-A of normal hearing ears for both cohorts of data.

Investigating Effects of SNHL in Two Age-Matched Cohorts of Older Adults (50-69 & 70-79)

To investigate the effect of SNHL in each independent cohort, we completed two analyses, one on ears that met one of our two SNHL inclusion criteria from the $2015-2016$ cohort who were age $50-69$ (inclusive), along with ears

in the same cohort and age range that met our normal criteria, and a second that did the same but for ears age 70-79 (inclusive) from the 2017-2020 cohort. Our lower age of 50 was based on the number of ears present in the cohort with SNHL (as the number of ears with SNHL below age 50 dropped substantially).

50-69 year old comparisons (2015-2016 NHANES cohort)

Audiometric and WAI-A data for adults 50-69-year-olds from the 2015-2016 NHANES cohort included in our analyses are shown in Figure 2. No statistically significant differences were observed between normal hearing ears and either SNHL group.

FIGURE 2. Adults 50-69-year-old from the 2015-2016 NHANES cohort. Upper: Audiometric thresholds of subjects in each of the three groups. Middle: p values for comparisons between normal and each SNHL group. Lower: Means plus and minus standard errors for each group.

70-79 year old comparisons (2017-2020 NHANES cohort)

Audiometric and WAI-A data for adults 70-79-year-olds from the 2017-2020 NHANES cohort included in our analyses are shown in Figure 2. At 103 of 107 frequencies, there are no significant differences were observed between the normal hearing ears (N=66) and ears with mild-to-moderate SNHL (N=45); the four frequencies 343, 364, 386, and 408 Hz have p values that range from 0.02 to 0.04. Similarly, at 102 of 107 frequencies, there are no significant differences between the normal hearing ears (N=66) and ears with severe-to-profound SNHL (N=8); the five frequencies 2000, 2059, 2119, 2181, and 2245 have p values that range from 0.03 to 0.05. We note that this is similar to what we might expect if there were no true differences.

FIGURE 2. Adults 70-79-year-old from the 2017-2020 NHANES cohort. Upper: Audiometric thresholds of subjects in each of the three groups. Middle: p values for comparisons between normal and each SNHL group. Lower: Means plus and minus standard errors for each group.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

For the 50-69-year-olds, no statistically significant differences were observed between normal hearing ears and either SNHL group. For the 70-79-year-olds, few statistically significant differences were observed between the normal hearing ears and ears with SNHL. These differences occurred at four frequencies (all 343-408 Hz) for the mild-to-moderate SNHL cohort and at five frequencies (all 2000-2245 Hz) for the severe-to-profound cohort. Since there were measurements at 107 frequencies, if there were no differences and associations were independent at each frequency, we would expect about 5 tests to have a p-value less than 0.05. With this older group, differences in sample size could also contribute to the results, as ears with severe-to-profound SNHL were notably fewer than the other two groups. Additionally, the differences observed were not consistent with those found by Attias and colleagues.² We observed trends toward reduced WAI-A in these ears from 750-2500 Hz and increased WAI-A from 5000-7000 Hz, while Attias and colleagues observed decreased WAI-A around 4000-5000 Hz in ears with severe-to-profound SNHL. Overall, our preliminary results suggest that SNHL is unlikely to have a notable effect on WAI-A.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Hannes Maier]: This analysis investigates the impact of sensorineural hearing loss on wideband acoustic immittance in age-matched groups with different degree of SNHL. For analysis data from two separate sets of WAI data in comparable age groups with SNHL ranging from normal hearing to severe-to-profound from the NHANES database were analyzed to separate the age effect from the SNHL effect.

The manuscript is clearly and concise written, the systematic difference in the two data sets was detected and taken into account, and statistics were adequate and carefully done.

Although it is stated that results are preliminary, this work is a strong argument against a direct SNHL effect on WAI results independent of age.

[Gabrielle Merchant]: Thanks for this, Hannes!

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[Shawn Goodman]: I understand the logic behind the number of expected p values less than .05, given the number of comparisons performed. What is less clear to me is the expected distribution of said p values. Under the assumption of no differences between groups and independent comparisons, I would expect the p values with values < 0.05 to be distributed randomly across the frequency comparisons. However, the observed p values with values < 0.05 are clustered. This may be due to the strong correlations between WAI-A of nearby frequencies, but is it also consistent with true changes in small, localized frequency regions? For the full paper, of course, consider a linear mixed model approach to statistics.

Additionally, regarding the Severe-to-Profound group, with an N of only 8 or 9, it seems unlikely that “significant” statistical results could be obtained unless the effect size was very large. It seems that if there is an effect of SNHL, the effect size is small. It might be interesting to approach the discussion from the perspective of effect size and statistical significance.

[Gabrielle Merchant]: Thanks Shawn – these are good and important point and will be considered for additional analyses when we publish!